

Employee Engagement: A Review Paper on Factors Affecting Employee Engagement in Social Media Context

Paper Id : 19146 Submission Date : 15/07/2024 Acceptance Date : 22/07/2024 Publication Date : 25/07/2024

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13347822

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Abstract

Background/Objectives: Since social media is stated being used in companies as a communication tool, the dynamics inside those spaces have evolved. This article's goal is to pinpoint the essential elements that drive employee engagement on different social media networks. **Methods and Statistical Analysis:** The review technique was employed by the researchers for this study. Researchers have identified key elements that are discussed in these research articles after going over about twenty-five scholarly and popular research papers and literature on employee engagement through social media. Our goal as reviewers is to make the body of existing material stronger. The writers have taken the results after carefully examining every aspect of each research report.

Results: Several elements related to engagements in the context of social media have been examined in this study work. Because this study addresses employee engagement, its conclusions will be helpful to any organization. Employee productivity is higher when they are engaged than when they are not. When utilizing social media for employee engagement, managers have to bear all of these considerations in mind. Anyone looking to learn more about employee engagement and how to use it to boost organizational performance may find this article useful. **Applications and Enhancements:** The findings of the study have potential applications in the future, such as reducing staff turnover and improving performance through the use of different engagement variables.

Keywords

Employee Engagement, Social Media

Introduction

Human resources are regarded as one of the most valuable assets for any company in this competitive age. There are many organizations in the world, but only those who recognize the value of their people resources go on to succeed. Employee engagement is a strategy that companies may use to acquire a competitive edge over rivals, claims **Baumruk (2004)**.

Gallup reports that teams with high levels of engagement experience 28% less internal theft and are 21% more productive than teams with low levels of engagement. Their ability to work together and have a positive attitude makes it possible for them to accomplish workplace objectives more successfully, which raises production levels.

According to **Martin (2013)**, in 2010, the Fortune 500 corporations embraced several social media platforms on average. According to predictions made by **Gartner (2013)**, half of the largest companies will have internal social networks that resemble Facebook by 2016. Given how quickly social media use is growing, efforts should be made to seize any possibilities that might help organizations.

As leaders and supervisors want to harness the value of the information and expertise that exists within their firms, social media platforms are being used more often throughout corporations (**Leonardi, 2015**). According to **Mark et al. (2014)**, social media is becoming more and more popular in businesses for a variety of reasons. According to **Gartner's (2013)** prediction, social media will revolutionize business data-sharing and communication. It was projected that internal social media will become just as significant to the business by 2016 as email and the phone.

Nowadays, social media has ingrained itself into our daily lives. We therefore frequently spend hours on social media. For many, social media serves as a need. Employers must to seize this opportunity and utilize social media as a means of encouraging employee involvement. Employee demands are met when these platforms are used for engagement activities like image sharing, awarding, and recognition.

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Theoretical Background

Employee engagement

The general definition of employee engagement is the degree of dedication and participation a worker has with their company. An engaged worker encourages his coworkers to succeed in the company's objectives while also being conscious of his own roles and obligations. Employees that are engaged strive for excellence in their work. Initially, Kahn (1990, p. 694) defined engagement at work as the "harnessing of organizational members' selves to their roles." Additionally, he stated that during job performances, "people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally" in involvement in his research.

Social Media

In general, social media refers to any web or mobile-based platform that allows for interactive communication between individuals or organizations and the sharing of user-generated content. Perhaps the first person to use the term "social media" was photographer, writer, strategist, hacker, and researcher Darrell Berry. Darrell claims that he coined the phrase in late 1994 while he was living in Tokyo and creating the online media environment Matisse.

Social media is now employed as a tactical tool rather than being a passing fad or obscure term. After realizing this, businesses began to use social media as networking platforms for hiring and employer branding. But now the time has come forward. Social media can now be utilized to interact with internal stakeholders, like as employees, in addition to customers. The arguments for and against using social media in the workplace are gradually dwindling, and social media is becoming more and more accepted in businesses. Tech Mahindra introduced "My Beat Plus," and Lenovo introduced "Lenovo Social Champions." In 1997, the phrase "social media" made its public debut (Bercovici, 2010). Online communication channels like blogs, discussion forums, social networking sites (Facebook, whatsapp, Twitter, LinkedIn), content-sharing websites (Youtube, Instagram, snapchat), and internal networking tools (Yammer) are all considered to be part of social media. The main purpose of these tools is to make it easier for users to create, edit, and share user-generated content. Particular social media platforms enable users to actively participate in the production, editing, and dissemination of user-generated content (Universal McCann, 2008).

Characteristics of social media

Connectivity: This quality demonstrates how the media can bring together or re-unite individuals who share interests in similar subjects and fields. Via this media, a range of media and access devices, such as computers, laptops, mobile phones, etc., can be connected around-the-clock. People that update their own accounts constantly and retweet and follow other people's remarks and status updates are instances of this quality.

Collaboration: People are able to work together and generate knowledge thanks to the connections made on this media. These kinds of partnerships can be closed or open. Wikipedia is an example of an open cooperation that brought hundreds of thousands of individuals together to create an online encyclopedia. One example of a closed collaboration is GovLoop, in which policy experts collaborate on particular issues.

Community: Communities are formed and maintained via cooperation and connectivity. Page 7 of 38 These communities can be used to raise awareness of a variety of issues, solicit input for policy, foster goodwill, or even get feedback on how public services are being provided. The traits have been visually represented below to illustrate how each trait is related to the others and how they depend on one another.

Need for Using Social Media

With the increasing penetration of ICTs in our day to day lives, we all have experienced connectedness. This connectedness brings several opportunities and also many challenges. These sites offer an opportunity to reach out to the customers, stakeholders in one go. The advantages of social media is so many. Many people use social media to fulfill their social need. Many organizations have started using these platforms to communicate with their employees. So there is a need of virtual engagement of the employees as the way they communicate to one another has changed. The no. of hours one spent using social media is also increasing so the employers should leverage this medium for engaging employees.

Objective of study

1. To identify and document the essential elements that drive employee engagement across various social media networks. Rationale: This objective aims to comprehensively gather and describe the key factors impacting employee engagement, providing a foundational understanding of how social media influences workplace dynamics.
2. To synthesize and strengthen the existing body of literature on employee engagement in social media by reviewing and analyzing approximately twenty-five scholarly and popular research papers. Rationale: This objective focuses on reviewing and integrating findings from multiple sources to create a robust framework that enhances the current understanding of social media's role in employee engagement.
3. To assess the practical applications of social media engagement strategies in organizations, including their potential to improve employee productivity and reduce staff turnover. Rationale: By evaluating the real-world implications of social media engagement, this objective aims to provide actionable insights for managers seeking to leverage social media to enhance organizational performance.

Review of Literature

Kahn's (1990) defined "**personal engagement**" "the harnessing of organization members' selves to their work roles; in engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performances" Kahn added that three psychological engagement conditions are necessary for an employee to be rightly engaged: meaningfulness (work elements), safety (social elements, including management style, process, and organisational norms) and availability (individual distractions)

Malash and leiter (1997) said that, engagement is a concept which is composed of three elements : energy , involvement and efficacy. Each of the three are direct reverse of one of the three burnout elements: which are emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and lack of efficacy

Robinson, Perryman and Hayday (2004) Engagement is described as "a positive attitude held by the employee towards the organization and its values". An engaged worker collaborates with coworkers to enhance job performance for the organization's benefit and is knowledgeable of the business environment. The company needs to foster a two-way interaction between employer and employee by developing engagement.

Chandani et al. (2016) found that when employees are engaged, there is a **decrease** in their **intentions to leave and an increase in creative work-related behavior**. Organizations can increase **employee commitment, decision-making, and opportunity thinking to increase engagement**. Employers must foster in their staff a feeling of camaraderie, positivity about their work, and involvement. Employee perspectives should be prioritized, and they should be given the chance to be heard. An **open culture** within the organization will also result from **senior leadership transparency**. It was recommended that firms utilize suitable training programs to make sure managers create a supportive environment that empowers their subordinates based on the research's above findings. Data from several sites showed that multicultural sites outperform monoculture sites and that R&D-enabled sites are more conducive to innovation.

Lappalainen et al. (2019) showed that an employee's **intrinsic qualities** have a greater influence on their level of engagement than do external circumstances. The relationship between engagement and conscientiousness, self-control, and social orientation was disproved by the analysis. Rather, analytical thinking, **extroversion, systems thinking, assertiveness, and leadership were the variables** linked to employee engagement.

Rai (2012) aims to comprehend social media and employee engagement concepts while providing an overview of Generation Y's traits and the variables that influence them in the workplace. Rai (2012) looked into how certain traits of Generation Y and their connectedness to the digital world affect organizational functions such as **internal communication, workplace atmosphere, and employee well-being**, which in turn

affects employees' commitment levels and perceptions of their organizations. For employee engagement to be successful, each of these procedures is essential. Thus, using social media for recruiting especially generation Y recruitment may yield substantial benefits for organizations.

Parry et al. (2013) suggested that social media holds potential for aiding in current employees' involvement. The results do, however, also imply that using social media to involve staff members won't work unless the organization's **leadership and culture** already value candid communication and involvement.

Sharma (2016) determined that employing workplace social media technology for employee engagement and collaboration goals can help organizations achieve their goals. Business social media serves as a platform for social networking among staff members and is also an excellent means of involving staff members in organizational activities like **ideation, problem-solving, and participatory decision-making**. As such, it can be a strategically implemented employee engagement program. But, establishing a "**open culture and transparency**" in which staff members not only "feel free" to share ideas and opinions but also "feel happy and involved" with high-touch points throughout their entire employment experience requires much more than simply investing in social media work tools.

Sievert et al. (2017) found that soft factors which frequently go hand in hand with a strong business **culture based on progressive leadership** are what drive employee engagement. Enterprise social media can promote these elements, which include **trust, personal accountability, and collaborative** cross-divisional work. These platforms allow employees to share their opinions as the "wisdom of the crowd" and operate based on the bottom-up philosophy. The study demonstrated how enterprise social media, a digital tool for employee engagement, can effectively boost overall employee engagement. On the other hand, the usage of internal social media increases employee engagement, and the establishment of these tools requires at least some level of current employee participation.

Men et al. (2020) Employee use of internal social media adds to increased levels of perceived **organizational transparency and identity**, which in turn boosts employee engagement, according to research on the benefits of enterprise social media usage on results.

Employee engagement and Performance of Employees

The financial or non-financial results of an employee are directly related to the success and performance of the organization. This is known as employee performance. Numerous studies demonstrate that emphasizing employee engagement is a crucial strategy for improving worker performance.

Markos et al. (2010) show that there is a strong correlation between **organizational performance outcomes and employee engagement**. Businesses with engaged workers experience **lower staff attrition and lower employee desire** to leave, as well as increased customer satisfaction, productivity, profitability, and growth. Conversely, businesses with disgruntled workers lose out on wasted effort and talent, receive less dedication from staff, deal with a rise in absenteeism, and have worse productivity, operating and net profit margins.

Social media and employees performance

Cheng (2020) studied the association between employee inventive performance and social media use, as well as the psychological processes that underlie this relationship. The findings of the study confirmed that there was a strong correlation between social media use and innovative performance, and that this link was somewhat mediated by job involvement. These results clarify the relationship between employee innovative performance and social media use.

Methodology

The study's primary focus is on gathering, analyzing, and integrating findings from various scholarly and popular sources to identify key factors affecting employee engagement within social media platforms.

To begin with, the scope of the review is clearly defined by focusing on literature published in the last few years, ensuring that the study encompasses current and relevant insights. The review covers a range of disciplines and types of publications to provide a comprehensive understanding of the topic. Key databases such as Google

Scholar, JSTOR, and Scopus are identified as primary sources for collecting relevant literature.

A rigorous selection process is employed to filter the literature. The criteria for selection include relevance to the topic, methodological rigor, and the study's contribution to understanding the key factors influencing employee engagement. The data collection process involves conducting a thorough search using specific keywords like "employee engagement," "social media," "organizational performance," and "engagement factors." This process results in an initial list of articles, which is then screened to ensure alignment with the established criteria.

The analysis involves thematic synthesis to identify recurring themes and findings across the selected literature. The identified factors influencing employee engagement in social media contexts are categorized and analyzed

Result and Discussion The relevance and significance of each of these variables' influences cannot be demonstrated by a single fixed model since different employees place varying degrees of emphasis on the various factors that affect engagement. These differences could result from differences in personal and professional traits, diversity in gender and ethnicity, etc. Several employee engagement strategies, such as better induction programs, time to time training for new information, development programs, certification programs, and providing them with a realistic job preview, are some of the recommendations made in this article for new hires. Training of managers by social media experts to be able to utilize social media platform in better way, Appreciation, rewards and recognition should be considered on regular basis to engage employees.

Conclusion The study also demonstrates that a decrease in employees' intentions to leave and an increase in creative work-related behaviour follow from employee engagement. No matter how fantastic the program is, engaging employees is a long-term endeavor that cannot be completed in a single training session. When an organization has strong leadership, participation in decision-making can be increased. An open and honest workplace where staff members exchange information will foster confidence between staff members and management and improve staff engagement. This will eventually increase worker performance and organizational productivity.

The Significance Of The Study

The study helps to identify the factors which affect the employee engagement through social media which will help the managers to understand the perspective of employees and accordingly they can work on making policies. The study would also provide more clear insight of employee engagement through social media, and its impact on employee performance and organisational performance . since employee engagement leads to better performance of employees.

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